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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE CLINICAL PRESENTATION
OF CELIAC DISEASE IN CHILDREN**Dr Hamayon¹, Dr Zmeryalai², Dr Zahid ullah³^{1,2} Railway General Hospital, Rawalpindi³ Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To assess the clinical features of celiac disease in children.**Place and Duration:** In the Pediatric Medicine department, Railway General Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year duration from February 2019 to February 2020.**Materials and methods:** We performed a retrospective analysis of data from 70 patients who underwent a small intestine biopsy (SBB) with suspected celiac disease. Forty-six children confirmed celiac disease based on the criteria of the European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology & Nutrition (ESPGAN). 24 patients due to lack of observation, ambiguous response to a gluten-free diet (GFD) and non-specific histology were excluded from the study. Clinical signs and symptoms, anthropometry and laboratory tests were analyzed.**Results:** A total of 46 children with M: F = 1: 1.2 meet the diagnostic criteria for celiac disease. The mean age and onset of symptoms at diagnosis were 6.7 and 3.4 years, respectively. Chronic diarrhea, lack of development and pallor were the most common clinical symptoms occurring in 82.6%, 89% and 95.6% of children, respectively. Flatulence and clubbing were reported in 65.2% and 17.4% of patients. Four children who received rickets and three had swelling of the feet during a clinical trial. Weight and height <5th percentile occurred in 91.3% and 86.9% of patients, respectively. Hemoglobin <10 g / dl was found in 45 children and elevated ALT > 40 I.U. was present in 13 patients.**Conclusion:** Chronic diarrhea, poor growth and anemia are the three main clinical features in children with celiac disease. Diagnostic criteria must be met before determining celiac disease in a child because GFD is recommended for life.**Key words:** celiac disease, diarrhea, pallor, short stature, children**Corresponding author:****Dr. Hamayon,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Celiac disease (CD) is a lifetime gluten sensitive enteropathy. Has worldwide distribution, which is very widespread in the Caucasians¹⁻². In Europe and the United States, estimated prevalence ranges from 1:80 to 1: 300 children. People from Pakistan living in the UK and following a gluten-rich diet, have 2.9 times more celiac disease than Europeans. Celiac disease has a family tendency with a 10% risk of recurrence in first degree relatives³⁻⁴. The compliance rate for homozygous twins is > 70%. Celiac disease causes autoimmune damage to the intestinal mucosa with the gluten fraction of gliadin in wheat, barley and rye⁵⁻⁶. There are humoral and cellular immune mechanisms. Histological features include ciliary atrophy, crypt overgrowth, and plaque infiltration with chronic inflammatory cells. Mucosal damage is classified according to Marsh criteria as increased epithelial lymphocytes (IEL) (Marsh type-I), partial villic atrophy (Marsh type II), flat mucosa with complete villi loss and crypt hypertrophy (Marsh type III). Type IV Marsh lesions have the same histological features as Type III lesions, except that the crypts are hypoplastic⁷⁻⁸. Typical gastrointestinal symptoms in young children (<3 years) include chronic diarrhea, anorexia, flatulence and vomiting. These symptoms are often accompanied by malabsorption results such as poor growth, weight loss, anemia and osteopenia. Gastrointestinal symptoms are more common in older children and adolescents⁷ and include CNS symptoms such as short stature, unexplained iron deficiency anemia, late puberty and ataxia, peripheral neuropathy, headache, anxiety and depression. Some patients, first degree relatives who are usually diagnosed with celiac disease, are asymptomatic and classified as silent and latent celiac patients. Quiet CD patients are asymptomatic, but have positive evidence of villous atrophy and biopsy serology, while silent CD patients have normal but positive serological tests⁹⁻¹⁰. ESPGAN (European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology & Nutrition) criteria for diagnosing CD include CD-compatible small intestine biopsy (SBB) and response to gluten-free diet (GFD) (mandatory) and positive serology (supporting evidence) in the form of anti-gliadin (AGA), anti-endomysialial (EMA) and anti-tissue transglutaminase (tTG) antibodies in patients with clinical CD suspension. In addition,

laboratory evidence of malabsorption in the form of micronutrient deficiency is usually present in most patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted in the Pediatric Medicine department, Railway General Hospital, Rawalpindi for one year duration from February 2019 to February 2020. We retrospectively examined the data of 70 patients who had SBB because of suspected CD. The study included 46 children who confirmed the CD based on SBB and response to GFD during follow-up and positive serology (in most patients). 24 patients with no observation, ambiguous response to GFD, and non-specific histology were excluded from the study. Age at onset and onset, clinical signs and symptoms, anthropometry and laboratory studies, including complete blood count with peripheral smear, S / E, S / albumin, stool C / E, LFT and viral markers were analyzed.

RESULTS:

A total of 46 boys, 25 girls and 21 boys (M: F = 1: 1.2) meet the diagnostic criteria for CD. The average age at diagnosis was 6.7 and 15 patients (32.6%) were 10 years old (Table 1). Regarding the onset of symptoms, the average age was 3.4 years, and the majority of patients had symptoms before the age of 2 in 26 (56.5%) patients, 7 (15.2%) at 2-5 years of age, 11 (23.9%) at the age of 6-10 years and 2 patients (4.3%) after 10 years of age (Table 2). Chronic diarrhea was the major complaint for seeking medical treatment present in 38 (82.6%) children. Pallor and failure to thrive (FTT) were the two most common clinical symptoms in 44 (95.6%) and 41 (89%) children, respectively. Of the FTT patients, 34 patients had diarrheal complaints, while seven children were short stature. Nervousness and flatulence were observed in 33 (71.7%) and 30 (65.2%) patients Finger clubbing was present in 8 (17.4%) children. 4(8.7%) children presented with rickets and 3 (6.5%) had edema feet on clinical examination (Table-3). In terms of weight and height, this is the tenth percentile in 2 and 1 patients, respectively (Table 4). Hemoglobin 40 IU. It was found in 13 patients (28.2%). Among these ALT 41–60 I.U. It was > 60 IU in 11 patients and only 2 patients. (Table 6).

Table 1: Age at Diagnosis (n = 46)

Age (years)	=n	%age
< 5	15	32.66
5 – 10	21	45.7
>10	10	21.7

Table 2: Age at Onset of Symptoms (n = 46)

Age (years)	=n	%age
<2	26	56.5
2 – 5	7	15.2
6 – 10	11	23.9
>10	2	4.3

Table 3: Clinical Presentation (n = 46)

	=n	%age
Chronic Diarrhoea	38	82.6
Failure to Thrive	41 (34+7)	89.1
Pallor	44	95.6
Irritability	33	71.7
Abdominal distension	30	65.2
Clubbing	8	17.4
Rickets	4	8.7
Oedema	3	6.5

Table 4: Anthropometric Measurements (n=46)

	<5 th Centile	5 th –10 th Centile	>10 th Centile
Weight	42 (91.3%)	2 (4.3%)	2
Height	40 (86.95%)	5 (10.9%)	1

Table 5: Hemoglobin Level (g/dl) (n=46)

Hb (g/dl)	=n	%age
<7	18	39.1
7 – 10	25	54.3
>10	3	6.5

Table 6: Alanin Transaminase Level (n=46)

ALT (I.U.)	=n	%age
<40	33	71.7
41 - 60	11	23.9
>60	2	4.2

DISCUSSION:

It was confirmed that a total of 46 children had celiac disease. The average age at diagnosis was 6.7. In India, this is consistent with a study in which the average age of CD diagnosis in children is 6.7 years. This can also be compared to a study in Switzerland at 6.8 years old. In the Jordan study, the average age at diagnosis was 8.4 years. In our study, the average age of onset of symptoms was 3.4 and is similar to Jordan's study, which is 4.6 years old. Our study showed female dominance (25 girls and 21 boys) and is similar to data in most countries¹¹. This explains the autoimmune nature of celiac disease and the more frequent occurrence of immune disorders in women than in men. In our study, chronic clinical diarrhea, FTT, and progressive pallor were observed in 82.6%, 89.1% and 95.6% of children, respectively. These findings can be compared with an Indian study in which the percentage is 84%, 84% and 91%. In a study from

Turkey, diarrhea was the most common clinical feature in 81.7% of patients, which was consistent with our work. Children were 65.2% present, and these results of abdominal bloating, Turkish-like abdominal edema work as documented in 60.6% of patients. While anecdote was observed in 17.4% of patients in our study, this figure was reported as 26% in international data. Rickets and edema were found in 8.7% and 6.5% of children, respectively. In Jordan's report, 26% of patients with CD had rickets¹²⁻¹³. As stated above, this can be explained by late diagnosis in Jordan (average age of diagnosis, 6.8 years in our study, 8.4 years in the study in Jordan). Among patients with edema, 2 patients had chronic diarrhea, and one teenager had unexplained edema and hypoalbuminaemia as the only clinical manifestations of celiac disease. Weight and height in our study <5. the percentile was present in 91.3% and 86.9% of children. These findings are similar to Indian studies, showing 87% waste and 60%

growth¹⁴. Data for Turkey showed low growth in 45.2% of patients with very low levels compared to our study. This can be explained by the very high incidence of malnutrition, which increases growth inhibition in children with celiac disease in our country. Hemoglobin <10 g / dl was present in 93.5% of children. Small hypochromic symptoms occurred in 84.8% of patients with anemia. This is in line with international data on nutritional anemia in patients with CD¹⁵. Slight changes in alanine aminotransminase (ALT) levels were observed in 28.1% of cases; this is consistent with another study in which the value is 38.3%. There were 2 people with type I diabetes (IDDM) and a child with Down syndrome, clearly associated with CD. We also haven't found a case of herpes dermatitis, which is a clinical symptom of CD and is more common in adults than childhood CDs.

CONCLUSION:

These are the three main clinical presentations in children with celiac disease are chronic diarrhea, failure to thrive and anemia. Diagnostic criteria must be met before determining celiac disease in a child because a lifetime gluten-free diet is recommended.

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